

The Influence of Competency, Compensation and Work Discipline on Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable in Fishery Business Expert Polytechnic Lecturers (Poltek Aup)

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Abstract:- Lecturers play a critical part in a college since their execution contributes to the advance of the college. Therefore, universities demand that lecturers have high work enthusiasm, as well as tenacity in their work, high competence and high work discipline, but unfortunately there are still many university managements who do not pay enough attention to the problem of lecturer job satisfaction. The purpose of this study is to ascertain how competency, pay, and work habits affect lecturers' performance, with the variable of job satisfaction acting as an intervening factor. Associative quantitative structural equation modeling (SEM) with Smart-PLS 4.1.0 software is the research methodology utilized. The 168 permanent lecturers at the Fisheries Business Expert Polytechnic (POLTEK AUP) comprised the study's population. With a total sample size of 120 respondents, the convenience sampling method—a non-probability sampling technique—was utilized in this investigation. The findings of the study demonstrate that competency, compensation, and work discipline all positively impact work satisfaction. Lecturer's performance is positively and significantly impacted by competency, compensation, work discipline, and job happiness. The impact of compensation, work discipline, and competency on lecturers' performance might be mitigated by work satisfaction.

Keywords:- Competency, Compensation, Work Discipline, Job Satisfaction, Lecturer's Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The goal of higher education as a formal educational setting is to generate qualified human resources (HR) with the expertise, skills and master the technology needed by the world of work. For this reason, universities have a mission to achieve national education goals as mentioned in the Republic of Indonesia's Regulation Number 87 of 2014 by the Minister of Education and Culture on study programs and postsecondary institutions, namely: (1) Preparing students to become members of society who have professional academic abilities who can apply, develop and create science and

technology; (2) Develop and disseminate science and technology and strive to use it to improve people's living standards and enrich national culture. This shows that the role of higher education is very important in terms of its mission, namely enlightening people's lives.

The existence of the Fisheries Business Expert Polytechnic (POLTEK AUP) as a technical implementation unit of the Maritime and Fisheries Human Resources Development Agency (BPSDMKP) of the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries is an educational institution that organizes the Diploma IV program with 3 (three) majors, namely Fishing Technology (TPI), Fisheries Product Processing Technology (TPH) and Aquatic Resources Management Technology (TPS) which produces graduates who have competencies or expertise in accordance with the scientific field, namely graduates who are reliable in the field of Fisheries Communication and Extension to support national fisheries development activities as well as support the activities of the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries and also Regional Governments in carrying out fisheries and marine development activities through participatory community service activities.

Lecturers play a critical part in a college since their execution contributes to the advance of the college. Subsequently, colleges request that lecturers have tall work excitement, as well as tirelessness in their work, high competence and high work teach, but shockingly there are still numerous college administrations who don't pay sufficient consideration to the issue of work satisfaction. On the off chance that a college or company pays somebody a compensation underneath the normal of what other individuals get, at that point that individual may feel disappointed, so numerous considers have found that compensation could be a work characteristic that's frequently cited as a source of disappointment.

If compensation is managed well, compensation will help the company to achieve its goals, maintain and maintain employees well. On the other hand, without sufficient

compensation, existing employees are very likely to leave the company and reassignment is not easy (Rivai, 2013). Compensation is one of the factors that influences employee job satisfaction. According to Yani (2012:139) compensation is payment in the form of financial and non-financial forms to motivate employees to have a good work spirit so that the productivity gotten by the company remains stable and increases. Compensation in financial form is in the form of wages or salaries while non-financial compensation such as insurance, social assistance, pensions and education.

Compensation will always be linked to the quantity, quality and benefits of the services provided by the lecturer. For some universities, compensation for lecturers can influence how much of a college's goals the lecturer can achieve. The welfare of lecturers will influence the survival of the higher education institution. Lecturers who have good performance are expected to be motivated to carry out their duties well and be able to meet predetermined targets.

One of the reasons that is quite dominant in influencing performance is the job satisfaction factor. An increase in job satisfaction among lecturers certainly has an impact on the performance they demonstrate. Handoko (2001) expressed that there are contrasts between workers who have work fulfillment and those who don't. Workers who feel fulfillment in their occupations tend to have superior records of participation and compliance with directions, but are less dynamic in partaking in union exercises. These representatives too more often than not have way better execution compared to workers who are not fulfilled with their work. Apart from being influenced by compensation and lecturer competence, it can be influenced directly or indirectly by work discipline. Mashudi (2019) stated that work teach can be summarized, that work teach is exceptionally imperative in a company in carrying out its obligations to realize the company's objectives. The point of this investigate is to decide the impact of competency, compensation and work discipline on performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable for lecturers at the Fisheries Business Expert Polytechnic (POLTEK AUP).

➤ *Competency*

Spencer (in Kusuma, 2017: 83), competence is defined as an underlying characteristic of a person that is causally related to the effectiveness of an individual's performance, or as a causal effect that is used as a benchmark, effective, and better performance in the workplace or in certain situations. At the same time, according to Dessler (2018: 183), competence is defined as demonstrable characteristics that include knowledge, skills and behaviors that can produce performance and achievement. According to the Regulation of the Government of the Republic of Indonesia No. 19 2005, the dimensions of competence are pedagogical competence, personality competence, professional competence and social competence.

➤ *Compensation*

Compensation is something that representatives get for the administrations they contribute to their work. They contribute what they think is important, both their vitality and their information. A worker who carries goods feels like he is contributing to his work. For moving goods from one place to another, they will receive adequate compensation for their work. Something that is valuable for employees is the knowledge and skills they possess which are used as a basis for demanding their rights as workers (Bangun, 2012: p. 13). The compensation dimension consists of direct compensation and indirect compensation (Hasibuan, 2007; Wibowo, 2009; Mondy et al, 2005).

➤ *Work Discipline*

Discipline is the activities or exercises of administration to meet organizational measures. Discipline could be a sort of preparing to progress and shape employees' information and behavior so that they are willing to undertake and work together and accomplish superior (Werther & Davis, 2003: 433). The most point of discipline is to empower workers to act suitably within the work environment where fitting behavior is characterized as compliance with rules and methods (Dessler, 2018: 607). According to Prijodarminto (2004) the dimensions of work discipline consist of attitudes, behavior and responsibility.

➤ *Lecturer's performance*

According to Suwatno & Donni (2016: 197) performance is a systematic description of the strengths and weaknesses of individual or group work. Although there are technical problems (such as choice of format) and human problems (such as taxi driver resistance and interpersonal barriers), not all performance evaluators can overcome them. According to Gunawan (2012) there are several dimensions that can be known in the role of lecturers in improving abilities in the teaching and learning process, namely the dimensions of lecturer's performance consisting of quality of work, accuracy of work, and initiative in work, and also ability in work and communication.

➤ *Job Satisfaction*

According to As'ad (2004) job satisfaction is "a person's feelings about work". This means that this understanding of job satisfaction sees job satisfaction as a person's interaction with the work environment. Job satisfaction prioritizes work over salary, although salary is important (Robbins & Judge, 2009). The dimensions of job satisfaction consist of work environment, supervision, and recognition (Hasibuan, 2007; Luthans, 2005; Robbins, 2009).

➤ *Hypothesis*

The proposed research hypothesis is as follows:

- H₁ : Competence influences job satisfaction of AUP POLTEK lecturers.
 H₂ : Compensation influences job satisfaction of AUP POLTEK lecturers.

- H₃ : Work discipline influences the satisfaction of AUP POLTEK lecturers.
- H₄ : Job satisfaction influences the performance of AUP POLTEK lecturers.
- H₅ : Competence influences the performance of AUP POLTEK lecturers.
- H₆ : Compensation influences the performance of AUP POLTEK lecturers.
- H₇ : Work discipline has a significant effect on the performance of AUP POLTEK lecturers.
- H₈ : Competence influences the performance of AUP POLTEK lecturers through job satisfaction as an intervening variable.
- H₉ : Compensation influences the performance of AUP POLTEK lecturers through job satisfaction as an intervening variable.
- H₁₀ : Work discipline has a significant effect on the performance of AUP POLTEK lecturers through job satisfaction as an intervening variable.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The sort of investigate that will be utilized is affiliated quantitative investigate, to be specific inquire about that inquires approximately the relationship between two or more variable. The relationship utilized in this inquire about could be a causal relationship. A causal relationship could be a causal relationship, which comprises of independent variable (affecting factors) and dependent (impacted factors) (Sugiyono, 2019:65). The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of variables competency, compensation and work discipline on job satisfaction and its impact on performance at the Fisheries Business Expert Polytechnic (POLTEK AUP).

The main population of this study was all permanent lecturers at the Fisheries Business Expert Polytechnic (POLTEK AUP), a total of 168 people in December 2023. In this study, non-probability sampling method or convenience sampling method was used for sampling. Sekaran (2006) stated that convenience sampling means collecting information from members of the population who are willing to provide information. Based on the Slovin formula with a leeway percentage used of 5%, a sample size of 118 respondents was obtained, but in this study the sample size was rounded up to 120 respondents.

The explanatory strategy utilized is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).. SEM could be a factual procedure for testing complex connections between factors and assessing demonstrate fit. SEM will be utilized to construct and test a hypothetical demonstrate that captures the relationship between inquire about factors and different variables in each gather (Santoso & Indrajaya, 2022). Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) technique with Smart-PLS 4.1.0 software was used to evaluate the collected samples. In the PLS method, the analysis technique used

includes three stages, namely outer model analysis, inner model analysis, and hypothesis testing.

III. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Analysis of Research Results*

The studies records changed into processed the usage of SmartPLS 4.1.0 which changed into achieved in stages, specifically the Measurement Model and the Structural Model.

➤ *Assessing the Outer Model or Measurement Model*

The outer model or measurement model explain how every indicator pertains to its latent variable. The measurement model is contained within side the validity and reliability test.

• *Validity Test*

The validity test on this studies makes use of a convergent validity test and a discriminant validity test. Convergent validity is associated with the precept that measurements of a assemble must be fairly correlated, at the same time as discriminant validity is associated with the precept that measurements of various constructs must now no longer be fairly correlated (Abdillah & Jogiyanto, 2016).

✓ *Convergent Validity Test*

Convergent validity is the loading factor number that a latent variable has on its indicators which functions to decide the validity of a construct. Convergent validity has a loading factor parameter of > 0.70 and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of > 0.50 .

Based at the consequences of the convergent validity test in table 1 above, it can be explained that all statements on each variable, namely the competency, compensation, work discipline, job satisfaction and lecturer's performance variables, all have a loading factor value of > 0.70 so they are stated valid. Next, a test was carried out with AVE, which exhibit how much variance the manifest variable has in the latent construct. The standard value set ≥ 0.50 means that convergent validity is good and acceptable.

Based at the consequences of the AVE test in table 2 above, it can be known that all research variables have an AVE value > 0.50 , so it can be interpreted that all variables have good and acceptable construct validity.

✓ *Discriminant Validity Test*

Discriminant validity is the position of isolation of an index in measuring the instrument construct. To test discriminant validity, it can be done using the Fornell-Larker Criterion test, videlicet by comparing the root value of AVE with other model constructs. However, it can be concluded that it has good discriminant validity.

If the number is lesser than the correlation value between the constructs and the others.

Based on the results of the Fornell-Larker criterion test, it can be known that the value of the root AVE and the correlation between the constructs of all variables have a higher value of the correlation coefficient for each variable than the value of Due to the correlation coefficient with the others variables, we can therefore conclude that the model has good discriminant validity.

• *Reliability test*

Reliability test functions to measure the reliability and stability of an indicator across multiple measurement variables. This study used Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability criteria, with each criterion greater than 0.70. From the reliability test results, it can be known that all variables have Cronbach's alpha value greater than 0.70 and composite reliability value greater than 0.70, so all variables in this study can be considered reliable.

➤ *Structural Model (Inner Model)*

After conducting the reflectance measurement test, evaluate the structural model (inner model). Structural model testing is performed using R² values to predict the strength of the structural model based on latent variables. The R² value can be known in Table 5 below:

Table 1. R-Square Value

Variable	R-Square
Job Satisfaction	0,516
Lecturer's performance	0,506

From table 1 above, the R² value of the job satisfaction variable is 0.516 or 51.6%. This means that job satisfaction is told by the variables of competence, compensation and work discipline by 51.6%, while the rest is 48.4% is influenced by other factors outside the exploration model. The R² value for the lecturer's performance variable is 0.506 or 50.6%. This means that lecturer's performance is affected by the variables of competency, compensation, work discipline and job satisfaction by 50.6%, while the rest is 49.4% is explained by other factors outside the exploration model.

➤ *Hypothesis testing*

The hypothesis testing is based on the results of Partial Least Square analysis by carrying out a Bootstrapping test utilize a level of confidence 90% (α = 10%), with a T-table (1.64).

➤ *Direct influence*

The comes about of the hypothesis test carried out can be known in table 2:

Table 2. Path Coefficients

	T statistics	t-tabel	P values	Results
KT -> KK	5,140	1,64	0,000	Accepted
KS -> KK	4,032	1,64	0,000	Accepted

DK -> KK	3,546	1,64	0,000	Accepted
KK -> KD	2,862	1,64	0,004	Accepted
KT -> KD	1,787	1,64	0,074	Accepted
KS -> KD	2,297	1,64	0,022	Accepted
DK -> KD	3,155	1,64	0,002	Accepted

Information:

KT = Competency

KS = Compensation

DK = Work Discipline

KD = Lecturer's performance

KK = Job Satisfaction

• *Hypothesis 1*

H1 : Competence impacts job satisfaction of AUP POLTEK lecturers.

Based on table 2, it can be known that the influence of competency on job satisfaction is gotten by a t-statistic value of 5.140 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.000 < 0.10, so H1 is accepted. This implies that competence influences positively and significantly on job satisfaction.

• *Hypothesis 2*

H2 : Compensation influences job satisfaction of AUP POLTEK lecturers.

Based on table 2 above, it can be known that the influence of compensation on job satisfaction is gotten by a t-statistic value of 4.032 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.000 < 0.10, so H2 is accepted. This implies that competition influences positively and significantly on job satisfaction.

• *Hypothesis 3*

H3 : Work discipline influences job satisfaction of AUP POLTEK lecturers.

Based on table 2 above, it can be known that the influence of work discipline on job satisfaction is gotten by a t-statistic value of 3.546 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.000 < 0.10, so H3 is accepted. This implies that work discipline influences positively and significantly on job satisfaction.

• *Hypothesis 4*

H4 : Job satisfaction influences the lecturer's performance of AUP POLTEK.

Based on table 2 above, it can be known that the influence of job satisfaction on lecturer's performance is gotten by a t-statistic value of 2.862 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.004 < 0.10, so H4 is accepted. This implies that job satisfaction influences positively and significantly on lecturer's performance.

• *Hypothesis 5*

H5 : Competence influences the lecturer's performance of AUP POLTEK.

Based on table 2 above, it can be known that the influence of competency on lecturer's performance is gotten by a t-statistic value of 1.787 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.074 <

0.10, so H5 is accepted. This implies that competence influences positively and significantly on lecturer’s performance.

• *Hypothesis 6*

H₆ : Compensation influences the lecturer’s performance of AUP POLTEK.

Based on table 2 above, it can be known that the influence of compensation on lecturer’s performance is gotten by a t-statistic value of 2.297 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.022 < 0.10, so H6 is accepted. This implies that compensation influences positively and significantly on lecturer’s performance.

• *Hypothesis 7*

H₇: Work discipline influences the lecturer’s performance of AUP POLTEK.

Based on table 2 above, it can be known that the influence of work discipline on lecturer’s performance is gotten by a t-statistic value of 3.155 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.002 < 0.10, so H7 is accepted. This means that work discipline influences positively and significantly on lecturer’s performance.

➤ *Indirect influence (via intervening variables)*

The indirect influence is the effect of the independent variable toward the dependent variable via an intervening variable or mediating variable. The intervening variable in the study is job satisfaction.

Table 3. Indirect Effects

	T statistics	t-tabel	P values	Results
KT -> KK -> KD	2,473	1,64	0,013	Able to mediate
KS -> KK -> KD	2,212	1,64	0,027	Able to mediate
DK -> KK -> KD	2,198	1,64	0,028	Able to mediate

Based on the results of hypothesis testing for indirect effects or through intervening variables, the results can be explained as follows:

• *Hypothesis 8*

H₈ : Competence influences the lecturer’s performance of AUP POLTEK through job satisfaction as an intervening variable.

Based on table 3 above, it can be known that the influence of competence on lecturer’s performance via job satisfaction as an intervening variable gotten a t-statistic value of 2.473 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.013 < 0.10, so H8 is accepted. This means that competence has a positive and significant effect on lecturer’s performance via job satisfaction as an intervening variable. Or in other words, job satisfaction is able

to mediate the effect of competence on the lecturer’s performance of AUP POLTEK.

• *Hypothesis 9*

H₉ : Compensation influences the lecturer’s performance of AUP POLTEK through job satisfaction as an intervening variable.

Based on table 3 above, it can be known that the effect of compensation on lecturer’s performance via job satisfaction as an intervening variable gotten a t-statistic value of 2.212 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.027 < 0.10, so H9 is accepted. This means that compensation has a positive and significant effect on lecturer’s performance via job satisfaction as an intervening variable. Or in other words, job satisfaction is able to mediate the effect of compensation on the lecturer’s performance of AUP POLTEK.

• *Hypothesis 10*

H₁₀ : Work discipline influences the lecturer’s performance of AUP POLTEK through job satisfaction as an intervening variable.

Based on table 3 above, it can be known that the influence of work discipline on lecturer’s performance through job satisfaction as an intervening variable obtained a t-statistic value of 2.198 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.028 < 0.10, so H10 is accepted. This means that work discipline influences positively and significantly on lecturer’s performance through job satisfaction as an intervening variable. Or in other words, job satisfaction is able to mediate the influence of work discipline on the lecturer’s performance of AUP POLTEK.

IV. DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

➤ *The influence of competence on job satisfaction*

The study results exhibit that the t-statistic value is 5.140 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.000 < 0.10. This means that competence has a positive and significant effect on the job satisfaction of AUP POLTEK lecturers. Therefore the hypothesis proposed in the study is accepted.

Competency is one of the most crucial elements in increasing the quality of higher education. Lecturer competency starts from the pedagogical, professional, personality and social abilities that must be inherent in a lecturer. According to Sedarmayanti (2013:126) competence is a fundamental characteristic possessed by a person that has a direct influence or can predict excellent performance. A lecturer must have the skills, abilities and skills of employees to carry out their duties and complete their responsibilities. Mastery of the basic concepts of a knowledge or skill will influence a person's job satisfaction so that they will continuously learn it. So, if someone feels they have high competence, then they will feel capable of completing their work well, thereby giving rise to job satisfaction and continuing to enrich their abilities. The results of the study are supported by study conducted by Cindrawasih (2019), Zainuddin, Riama & Oktarida (2015) and Wahyuni (2012)

which shows that competence influence positively and significantly on job satisfaction.

➤ *The effect of compensation on job satisfaction*

The study result exhibit that the t-statistic value is 4.032 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.000 < 0.10. This means that compensation influences positively and significantly on the job satisfaction of AUP POLTEK lecturers. Thus the hypothesis proposed in the study is accepted.

In general, the form of compensation is financial due to monetary expenditures made by the organization. Compensation can be given directly to employees, or indirectly, where employees receive compensation in non-monetary form. Suparyadi (2015:271) says that compensation is the total compensation received by an employee or person as appreciation for the contribution they have made to the organization, both financial and non-final. Compensation is one of the factors that can influence lecturer's job satisfaction. Having rewards or appreciation for lecturers and education staff will make them feel satisfied. The higher the compensation a person receives, the higher the level of job satisfaction. The results of the study are supported by research done by Nugraheni (2020), Cindrawasih (2019) and Ilyas (2011) which shows that compensation influences positively and significantly on job satisfaction.

➤ *The influence of work discipline on job satisfaction*

The study result exhibit that the t-statistic value is 3.546 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.000 < 0.10. This means that work discipline influences positively and significantly on the job satisfaction of AUP POLTEK lecturers. Thus the hypothesis proposed in this research is accepted.

Discipline is a condition that causes or encourages employees to act and carry out all activities in accordance with established rules. Farida and Hartono (2016:41) say that good discipline reflects a person's great sense of responsibility for the tasks given to him. Discipline is really required by both the individual concerned and the agency, because discipline really helps individuals to straighten out what can and cannot be conducted in an organization. Work discipline is understood as the lecturer's attitude towards the applicable rules. The application of this discipline results in lecturers who implement it showing success in the teaching process. Tasks are completed (Tri Dharma) and work and planning are completed well according to established procedures. With high work discipline, all assignments and work can be completed well so that it will provide job satisfaction for lecturers. So the higher the work discipline, the higher the job satisfaction of AUP POLTEK lecturers. The results of the study are supported by research done by Muttaqin and Soeparto (2021), Rama (2023) and Dewi (2012) which exhibit that work discipline influences positively and significantly on job satisfaction.

➤ *The influence of job satisfaction on lecturer's performance*

The study result exhibit that the t-statistic value is 2.862 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.004 < 0.10. This means that job satisfaction influences positively and significantly on the lecturer's performance of AUP POLTEK. Therefore the hypothesis proposed in the study is accepted.

Job satisfaction is an assessment or reflection of a person's feelings towards their work. This can be known in a person's positive attitude towards their work and everything they encounter in their work environment. Sutrisno (2019:74) said that job satisfaction is an employee's attitude towards work which is related to working conditions, cooperation between employees, rewards received at work, and matters related to physical and psychological factors. If someone joins a university as a lecturer, they bring a number of wants, needs, desires and past experiences that combine to form job expectations. Job satisfaction shows the match between a person's expectations and the rewards provided for his work. Basically, job satisfaction is an individual thing, each individual will have a different level of satisfaction according to the value system that exists within him. This is due to the differences between each individual, the more aspects of the work that suit the individual's desires, the higher the level of satisfaction felt which will have an impact on increasing a person's performance. So the higher the job satisfaction, the higher the performance. The results of the study are supported by research done by Wahyuni (2012) and Cindrawasih (2019) which exhibit that job satisfaction influences positively and significantly on lecturer's performance.

➤ *The influence of competency on lecturer's performance*

The study result exhibit that the t-statistic value is 1.787 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.074 < 0.10. This means that competence influences positively and significantly on the lecturer's performance of AUP POLTEK. Therefore the hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted.

Improving work competency needs to be done within the organization. Lecturers who have work competencies tend to have good abilities in completing tasks and based on work targets given by the organization. This will certainly provide work enthusiasm within lecturers to continue carrying out work that can improve their performance. The higher the competency a lecturer has, the higher the lecturer's performance. The results of this study are supported by research done by Ilyas (2011) and Zainuddin, Riama & Oktarida (2015) which exhibit that competence influences positively and significantly on lecturer's performance.

➤ *The effect of compensation on lecturer's performance*

The study result exhibit that the t-statistic value is 2.297 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.022 < 0.10. This means that compensation influences positively and significantly on the lecturer's performance of AUP POLTEK. Therefore the hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted.

The positive influence of compensation on lecturer's performance exhibit that providing compensation can improve lecturer's performance. Compensation is an important factor for lecturers, because with this compensation they can meet their needs directly, especially their physiological needs. However, lecturers also hope that the compensation they receive is in accordance with their assessment of the sacrifices they have made to the organization. If lecturers' expectations regarding compensation can be realized by the organization, then lecturers will feel that they are treated fairly by the organization, so that they will continue to improve their performance. So the higher the compensation received, the higher the performance of AUP POLTEK lecturers. The results of this study are supported by research done by Cindrawasih (2019) and Zumali, Rahmat & Utami (2020) which exhibit that compensation influences positively and significantly on lecturer's performance.

➤ *The influence of work discipline on lecturer's performance*

The study result exhibit that the t-statistic value is 3.155 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.002 < 0.10. This means that work discipline influences positively and significantly on the lecturer's performance of AUP POLTEK. Therefore the hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted.

The application of discipline in an organization is intended for all employees in the organization to be willing and voluntarily obey and obey all the rules and regulations that apply in the organization without coercion. With high discipline, all work can be completed well without any time delays or delays. This condition indicates that work discipline also determines the results and productivity of lecturers' work. The higher the work discipline that lecturers have, the easier it will be for them to complete the Tridharma tasks, namely education and teaching, research and community service, so that their performance will increase. The results of this study are supported by research done by Zumali, Rahmat & Utami (2020) and Indirasari (2021) which exhibits that work discipline influences positively and significantly on lecturer's performance.

➤ *The influence of competency on lecturer's performance through job satisfaction as an intervening variable*

The study result exhibit that the t-statistic value is 2.473 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.013 < 0.10. This means that competence influences positively and significantly on the performance of AUP POLTEK lecturers through job satisfaction. Or in other words, job satisfaction is able to mediate the influence of competence on lecturer's performance. Therefore the hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted.

Competence can directly influence job satisfaction and is an important factor in influencing lecturer job satisfaction. Lecturers who have high competence will of course be able to complete all their assignments and work thereby giving the lecturer a sense of satisfaction. This will of course have an impact on lecturer's performance becoming better. Thus,

competence, both directly and indirectly, can influence lecturer's performance. Job satisfaction is a variable that acts as a mediating variable between competence and performance. The higher the level of lecturer competence, the higher the level of satisfaction felt and this will positively influence their performance as a lecturer. The results of this study are supported by research done by Marsana (2008) and Zainuddin, Riama & Oktarida (2015) which exhibits that competence influences positively and significantly on lecturer's performance which is mediated by job satisfaction as an intervening variable.

➤ *The effect of compensation on lecturer's performance through job satisfaction as an intervening variable*

The study result exhibit that the t-statistic value is 2.212 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.027 < 0.10. This means that compensation influences positively and significantly on the performance of AUP POLTEK lecturers through job satisfaction. Or in other words, job satisfaction is able to mediate the influence of compensation on lecturer's performance. Therefore the hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted.

Compensation is an important part of an organization as a financial responsibility that must be given to employees who have completed their duties. An organization that implements an appropriate compensation system will provide a sense of satisfaction to its employees and be able to motivate its employees to work better. Compensation can directly influence lecturer's performance. Providing compensation that is in line with the lecturers' expectations will certainly give the lecturers a sense of satisfaction. The higher the job satisfaction obtained and felt, the higher the possibility that lecturers will provide their best performance, and vice versa, if lecturers lack job satisfaction, it will be difficult for them to provide their best performance. The results of this study are supported by research done by Ilyas (2011) and Lubis, Pasaribu, Tupti (2020) which exhibits that compensation influences positively and significantly on lecturer's performance which is mediated by job satisfaction as an intervening variable.

➤ *The influence of work discipline on lecturer's performance through job satisfaction as an intervening variable*

The study result exhibit that the t-statistic value is 2.198 > 1.64 with a sig. of 0.028 < 0.10. This means that work discipline influences positively and significantly on the lecturer's performance of AUP POLTEK through job satisfaction. Or in other words, job satisfaction is able to mediate the influence of work discipline on lecturer's performance. Therefore the hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted.

Work discipline is an attitude, behavior and actions that comply with written and unwritten regulations. Good discipline reflects a person's sense of responsibility for the tasks assigned to him. High work discipline can provide job satisfaction for a person because with this discipline all work

can be done well and completed on time. This will of course affect its performance. The higher the work discipline, the higher the perceived job satisfaction and the higher the performance. The results of this study are supported by research done by Nirmalasari, Amelia (2020) which exhibits that work discipline influences positively and significantly on lecturer's performance which is mediated by job satisfaction as an intervening variable.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

➤ Conclusion

Based on the results of the study and discussion in the previous chapter, it can be concluded that competence, compensation and work discipline influence positively and significantly on the job satisfaction of AUP POLTEK lecturers. Job satisfaction influences positively and significantly on the lecturer's performance of AUP POLTEK. Competency, compensation, work discipline and job satisfaction influence positively and significantly on the lecturer's performance of AUP POLTEK. Competence, compensation and work discipline influence positively and significantly on the lecturer's performance of AUP POLTEK via job satisfaction as an intervening variable. Or in other words, job satisfaction is able to mediate the influence of competence, compensation and work discipline, which influences positively and significantly on the lecturer's performance of AUP POLTEK.

➤ Suggestion

The advice that writer can convey from the results of this research is that Institutions must ensure that lecturers provide lecture material according to the curriculum and syllabus, for example by reporting on the achievement of conformity of the material with the syllabus. Institutions must be able to provide lecturers with a decent life with the allowances received from the institution. Lecturers must carry out their duties well and complete them optimally without wasting time on other activities. Institutions must provide adequate classrooms, for example by providing good facilities, facilities and infrastructure so that lecturers will feel happy with the work they do. Lecturers must be able to understand the characteristics of cadets, for example by understanding the real life experienced by cadets on a daily basis so that when explaining the subject matter they can provide examples. For future researchers who want to study the same material, they should add or replace several variables such as education and training, organizational support, management support and others so that factors can be identified that can influence job satisfaction and lecturer's performance.

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